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Addendum to the 2016 key to the dwarfgobies (Teleostei: Gobiidae: *Eviota*)

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Abstract

Sixteen species of *Eviota* have been described since the comprehensive key to the 107 species in the genus by Greenfield & Winterbottom (2016). The additional species are listed and discussed, along with their diagnostic characters and photographs, and where they fit into the original key. Corrections and updates to the 2016 key are included.

Key words: taxonomy, ichthyology, coral-reef fishes, Indonesia, Indo-Pacific Ocean

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Introduction

Greenfield & Winterbottom (2016) published a key to 107 valid species of the gobiid genus *Eviota* described between 1871 and most of 2016 (hereafter called the 2016 key). Since that time, an additional 16 species have been described. Now with 123 valid described species, the genus *Eviota* is the second most speciose coral-reef fish genus (after *Gymnothorax* with 139 species), the sixth most speciose marine fish genus and the twentieth most speciose teleost genus. As a result of selective searches for microgobies, underwater photography, and collecting by diving researchers, many *Eviota* have been described recently, with 74 species described between 2009 and

2020. In addition, there are many undescribed species known, and many of those are in complexes currently represented by a single species. Greenfield (2017) provided a comprehensive overview of many facets of the biology of the genus.

Most of the new species added since 2016 are known only from the type locality or have very limited distributions. As discussed by Greenfield (2017), their relatively short pelagic larval duration, combined with a short lifespan and rapid turnover, provide the necessary ingredients for the development of restricted-range endemic species of *Eviota*.

For each new species, information is provided on the holotype, type locality, range, diagnostic characters, where it would be positioned in the 2016 key, and relevant differences from species with which it shares the couplet. Methods follow those reviewed in the 2016 key and Greenfield (2017). Data in parentheses refer to the dorsal/anal-fin formula, whether the pectoral-fin rays are branched or not, the length of the fifth pelvic-fin ray relative to the fourth, and the morphology of the male urogenital papilla, if other than non-fimbriate, non-cup-shaped, or non plate-like, e.g. (9/8, branched, 5th 20%, fimbriate).

Species added since the 2016 key

Eviota eyreae Greenfield & Randall, 2016

Eyre's Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 238067, 10.8 mm SL female; type locality Vatu-i-ra Island, Fiji; range: only known from type location (7/7, branched, 5th 10%).

This species keys to couplet 103 in the 2016 key, where it shares line 103a with *E. santanai*, the only other species of *Eviota* lacking both the IT and PITO pores and with the AITO pore not enlarged or paired; *E. eyreae* differs by having a dorsal/anal-fin formula of 7/7 (vs. 8/8), the fifth pelvic-fin ray about 10% of fourth (vs. absent), no dark spot over preural centrum (vs. present), and different live coloration.

Figure 1. *Eviota eyreae*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); live holotype (right, J. Eyre).

Figure 2. *Eviota santanai*, preserved holotype, Timor-Leste (left, D.W. Greenfield); live holotype (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Eviota erdmanni Tornabene & Greenfield, 2016

Erdmann's Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 238221, 11.8 mm SL male; type locality Ende, south Flores, Indonesia; range: only known from type location (9/8, branched, 5th absent, cup-like).

This species keys to couplet 74 in the 2016 key, with *E. latifasciata* and *E. dorsimaculata* (all lacking only the IT pore); *E. erdmanni* differs from both by having a dorsal/anal-fin formula of 9/8 (vs. 8/8), a cup-shaped urogenital papilla (vs. non-cup-shaped), and different live coloration.

Figure 3. *Eviota erdmanni*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh holotype (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 4. *Eviota latifasciata*, fresh, Palau (left, R. Winterbottom); *Eviota dorsimaculata*, fresh paratype, Marquesas Islands (right, J.T. Williams).

Eviota sodwanaensis Greenfield & Winterbottom, 2016

Sodwana Dwarfgoby

Holotype: ROM 72842, 13.6 mm SL male; type locality south of Uniform Reef, NNE Sodwana Bay, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa; range: Sodwana Bay to Aliwal Shoal, KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa (8/7, branched, 5th 20%).

This species keys to couplet 33 in the 2016 key, with *E. pardalota* and *E. rubriguttata* (all with a complete cephalic sensory-canal pore system); *E. pardalota* has two prominent dark spots on the pectoral-fin base when preserved (vs. absent) and lacks an obvious dark occipital spot (vs. present); *E. rubriguttata* has large red spots covering both dorsal fins in life (vs. absent), the fifth pelvic-fin ray absent (vs. present), and 17 pectoral-fin rays (vs. 15).

Figure 5. *Eviota sodwanaensis*, preserved paratype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh paratype (right, R. Winterbottom).

Figure 6. *Eviota pardalota*, fresh, Saudi Arabia (left, J.E. Randall); *Eviota rubriguttata*, fresh holotype, Japan (right, T. Suzuki).

Eviota bilunula Greenfield & Suzuki, 2016

Crescent Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 238065, 10.9 mm SL male; type locality Charlie's Garden, Viti Levu, Fiji; range: Fiji (7/7 or 8/7, unbranched, 5th 16.4%).

This species keys to couplet 60 in the 2016 key, with *E. flebilis*, *E. ancora*, and the two recently described species *E. imitata* and *E. lentiginosa* (all lacking only the IT pore); *E. bilunula* differs from all in having two distinctive black, crescent-shaped marks underneath the pectoral fin and a longer fifth pelvic-fin ray (15.9–16.4% vs. 9.7–12.9% in *E. flebilis*, 10% in *E. ancora*, or absent). It shares a thin dark bar at the caudal-fin base with *E. flebilis* (vs. no bar or an irregular blotch).

Figure 7. *Eviota bilunula*, preserved holotype; inset: crescent marks (left, D.W. Greenfield); Fiji (right, R. Whitworth).

Figure 8. *Eviota flebilis*, fresh holotype, Ryukyu Islands, Japan (left, K. Shibukawa); Ryukyu Islands, Japan (right, K. Yano).

Figure 9. *Eviota imitata*, preserved paratype (left, D.W. Greenfield); Raja Ampat, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Eviota imitata Greenfield, Tornabene & Erdmann, 2017

Imitator Dwarfgoby

Holotype: MZB 23844, 13.9 mm SL male; type locality Eagle Rock, Kawe, Raja Ampat, West Papua, Indonesia; range: only known from type location (7–9/7–8 usually 8/7, unbranched, 5th absent).

This species keys to couplet 60 in the 2016 key, with *E. flebilis*, *E. ancora*, and the two recently described species *E. bilunula* and *E. lentiginosa* (all lacking only the IT pore); *E. imitata* differs from all in having an irregular dark blotch at the caudal-fin base (vs. a thin dark bar or no bar). In addition, it differs by having three (one specimen with 4) ventral dark postanal spots (vs. 5 in *E. flebilis* and *E. bilunula*). It shares with *E. lentiginosa* the absent fifth pelvic-fin ray and ray formula 8/8 (vs. fifth present and 8/7 in *E. flebilis*, *E. ancora*, and *E. bilunula*).

Eviota pictifacies Greenfield & Erdmann, 2017

Paintedface Dwarfgoby

Holotype: MZB 23883, 14.9 mm SL female; type locality Teluk Saleh, Tanjung Ntjanga, Sumbawa, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia; range: Eastern Indonesia, from Sumbawa to North Sulawesi and West Papua (9/8, branched, 5th poorly developed).

This species keys to couplet 14 in the 2016 key, with *E. fallax*, *E. karaspila*, and *E. melasma* (all with a complete cephalic sensory-canal pore system); *E. pictifacies* has distinctive eye coloration, with bold dark-brown-and-white markings; it is most similar to *E. melasma*, but its pelvic-fin rays are shorter and stouter and bound by membranes (vs. not connected), and it has distinctive black marks on the underside of the head (vs. absent); *E. pictifacies* differs from *E. fallax* in having two separate orange spots behind the eye (vs. a single, rounded orange spot) and pelvic-fin rays that are stouter and bound by membranes (vs. not connected). *Eviota karaspila* is distinctive, with a very pale live coloration, a very prominent occipital spot, and no distinct orange patch behind the eye.

Figure 10. *Eviota pictifacies*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); Sumbawa, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 11. *Eviota fallax*, preserved holotype, West Papua, Indonesia (left, D.W. Greenfield); Bali, Indonesia (right, G.R. Allen).

Figure 12. *Eviota melasma*, Australia (left, A. González-Cabello); *Eviota karaspila*, Fiji (right, J. Eyre).

***Eviota lentiginosa* Greenfield & Randall, 2017**

Freckled Dwarfgoby

Holotype: QM I.40817, 13.4 mm SL male; type locality Sydney Bay, Norfolk Island, Australia; range: Norfolk Island, Australia (8/8, unbranched, 5th absent, rounded plate-like).

This species keys to couplet 60 in the 2016 key, with *E. flebilis*, *E. ancora*, and the two recently described species *E. bilunula* and *E. imitata* (all lacking only the IT pore); *E. lentiginosa* differs from all in the fresh coloration and having a rounded plate-like urogenital papilla (vs. non-plate-like). It shares with *E. imitata* the absent fifth pelvic-fin ray and ray formula 8/8 (vs. fifth present and 8/7 in *E. flebilis*, *E. ancora*, and *E. bilunula*).

Figure 13. *Eviota lentiginosa*, fresh holotype (left, J.E. Randall); *Eviota ancora*, fresh holotype, Japan (right, T. Suzuki).

***Eviota maculosa* Greenfield, Tornabene, Gómez-Buckley & Erdmann, 2018**

Polkadot Dwarfgoby

Holotype: MZB 24615, 16.3 mm SL male; type locality Teluk Saleh, Sumbawa, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia; range: Sulawesi, Sumbawa, West Papua (Indonesia) and Pohnpei (Micronesia). Individuals with a similar appearance are known from throughout eastern Indonesia and eastward to Australia (9/8, branched, 5th 6.7–17.5%).

This species keys to line 81a in the 2016 key, with *E. punctulata* (lacking only the IT pore). The first dorsal fin of *E. punctulata* is crossed by rows of fine dark spots, whereas the first dorsal fin of larger males of *E. maculosa* have distinctive large, round, black spots on the spines; similar spotting, although usually smaller, is typically present on the second dorsal and caudal fins.

Figure 14. *Eviota maculosa*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); Sumbawa, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 15. *Eviota punctulata*, preserved, Lau Group, Fiji (left, D.W. Greenfield); Fiji (right, M.V. Erdmann).

***Eviota gunawanae* Greenfield, Tornabene, Erdmann & Pada, 2019**

Tiene's Dwarfgoby

Holotype: MZB 24002, 15.9 mm SL male; type locality Karas Island, Fakfak Peninsula, West Papua, Indonesia; range: only known from type location (8/7, unbranched, 5th 10%).

This species keys to line 90b in the 2016 key, with *E. tetha* (lacking only the IT and NA pores, with the AITO pore positioned far forward and opening anteriorly); *E. gunawanae* differs in live coloration and having 16 pectoral-fin rays (vs. 14 [6] or 15[3]), the fifth ray 10% of fourth (vs. absent or rudimentary), the dark spot at the base of the caudal fin larger and extending anteriorly as a partially overlapping paired spot (vs. restricted to the posterior end of the hypural plate), only a few scattered melanophores at the pectoral-fin base (vs. a narrow horizontal line of melanophores crossing the pectoral-fin base), and the anterior margins of the scales outlined with melanophores (vs. not darkly outlined).

Figure 16. *Eviota gunawanae*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); West Papua, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 17. *Eviota tetha*, preserved holotype, West Papua, Indonesia (left, D.W. Greenfield); West Papua, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

***Eviota dalyi* Greenfield & Gordon, 2019**

Amirante Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 246480, 6.9 mm SL female; type locality N. of D'Arros Island, Amirante Islands, Republic of Seychelles; range: only known from type location (8/7, branched, 5th 20%, flat, rounded plate-like).

This species keys to couplet 70 in the 2016 key (lacking only the IT pore), being a third alternative with a lower fin-ray count, dorsal I,8 (vs. I,9 or I,10).

Figure 18. *Eviota dalyi*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh holotype (right, R. Daly).

***Eviota amamiko* Fujiwara, Suzuki & Motomura, 2019**

Amamiko Dwarfgoby

Holotype: KPM-NI 36630, 10.4 mm SL female; type locality Kakeroma-jima, Amami Islands, Japan; range: Ryukyu Islands, Japan (8/8, branched, 5th rudimentary).

This species keys to line 6b in the 2016 key, with *E. jewettae* and recently described *E. angustifascia* (lacking all cephalic sensory-canal pores). It differs by having a rudimentary fifth pelvic-fin ray (vs. >10%), and 5 internal dark body bars, several branching into Y- or X-shapes (vs. 5 or 6 unbranched orange or reddish body bars in *E. jewettae* and narrow white lines between bars in *E. angustifascia* [see Fig. 27 below]).

Figure 19. *Eviota amamiko*, fresh holotype, KPM-NR 107971 A & B (left); fresh paratype (right), © Kanagawa Prefectural Museum of Natural History, photographs by Hiroshi Senou).

Figure 20. *Eviota jewettae*, fresh paratype, Palau (left, R. Winterbottom); Raja Ampat, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

***Eviota perspicilla* Fujiwara, Suzuki & Motomura, 2019**

Glasses Dwarfgoby

Holotype: KAUM-I. 124386, 13.5 mm SL male; type locality Kataura, Kasasa, Minami-satsuma, Kagoshima, Japan; range: Satsuma Peninsula, Koshiki Islands, Osumi Islands, and Amami Islands, Japan (9/8, branched, 5th rudimentary).

This species keys to line 69a in the 2016 key, with *E. queenslandica* (lacking only the IT pore). It differs by a distinct dark caudal-peduncle spot over the preural centrum (vs. a small, poorly-defined dark spot), lacking dark spots under the pectoral-fin base (vs. present), and in having two small, translucent, white, circular spots on the first dorsal-fin base (vs. absent).

Figure 21. *Eviota perspicilla*, fresh holotype (left and right, KAUM).

Figure 22. *Eviota queenslandica*, fresh, Australia (left, J.B. Hutchins); fresh, Palau (right, R. Winterbottom).

***Eviota pseudaprica* Winterbottom & Greenfield, 2020**

False Sunny Dwarfgoby

Holotype: ROM 77495, 13.3 mm SL male; type locality Uchelbeluu Reef, southeast Koror Island, Palau; range: Palau and Raja Ampat, West Papua, Indonesia (9/8, branched, 5th 65–85%).

This species keys to couplet 49 in the 2016 key, being a third alternative with an unusual cephalic sensory-canal pore pattern with only paired PITO and SOT pores. It shares that branch with recently described *E. amphipora*, but differs substantially in fresh coloration and by having a well-developed fifth pelvic-fin ray (vs. rudimentary).

Figure 23. *Eviota pseudaprica*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); West Papua, Indonesia (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 24. *Eviota amphipora*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh holotype (right, M.V. Erdmann).

***Eviota amphipora* Greenfield & Erdmann, 2020**

Twinpore Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 247238, 9.8 mm SL male; type locality Sideia patch reef, Milne Bay, Papua New Guinea; range: only known from type location (9/8, branched, 5th rudimentary).

This species keys to couplet 49 in the 2016 key, being a third alternative with an unusual cephalic sensory-canal pore pattern with only paired PITO and SOT pores. It shares that branch with recently described *E. pseudaprica* (above), but differs substantially in fresh coloration and by having a rudimentary fifth pelvic-fin ray (vs. well-developed).

***Eviota marteynae* Greenfield & Erdmann, 2020**

Red Star-eye Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 247235, 10.3 mm SL male; type locality Kaafa-haa, Laamu Atoll, Maldives Islands; range: Laamu Atoll, Maldives Islands (8/8, branched, 5th 7–12%).

This species keys to line 73b in the 2016 key, with *E. shibukawai* (lacking only the IT pore). It differs by having a greater body depth and a deeper caudal peduncle, a more pointed first dorsal fin, and in live coloration, in particular having electric-blue spots on the body and fins.

Figure 25. *Eviota marteynae*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh paratype (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Figure 26. *Eviota shibukawai*, preserved holotype; fresh holotype, Iriomote-jima, Japan (both T. Suzuki).

Eviota angustifascia Greenfield & Erdmann, 2020

Whiteline Dwarfgoby

Holotype: CAS 247247, 10.6 mm SL male; type locality Tavunasici, Lau Group, Fiji; range: Lau Group, Fiji and north coast of New Guinea (9/8, unbranched, 5th 10.1–17.2%).

This species keys to line 6b in the 2016 key, with *E. jewettae* and recently described *E. amamiko* (lacking all cephalic sensory-canal pores). It differs by having a 9/8 ray formula (vs. 8/8), and the body crossed by 5 narrow white lines separating wider dark bars, with the dark bar under the posterior dorsal fin wider than eye diameter (vs. the bar equal to eye diameter in *E. jewettae* and no white lines in *E. amamiko*). It further differs from *E. amamiko* by having a developed fifth pelvic-fin ray (vs. rudimentary) and no branching internal dark bars (vs. present).

Figure 27. *Eviota angustifascia*, preserved holotype (left, D.W. Greenfield); fresh holotype (right, M.V. Erdmann).

Errata for the 2016 key:

- 4a (3) -- formula 8/8 or 9/8–9 [modal 9/8, should be “formula 8/8 [8/8,”
- 5a (3) -- Greenfield & Winterbottom, 2018 should be “2016”
- 24a (12) -- should be “24a (23)”
- 29a (28) -- *E. readeri* should be “*E. readerae*”
- Fig. 31 legend -- *E. readeri* should be “*E. readerae*”
- 38a (36) -- should lead to “39” not 38
- 38b -- should lead to “44” not 43
- 39a (38) -- should lead to “40” not 39
- 39b -- should lead to “41” not 40
- 41a (39) -- should lead to “42” not 41
- 41b -- should lead to “43” not 42
- 42a (41) -- change Speckled to “Dusted”
- 42b -- change Speckled to “Dusted” and add “plate-like” after 5th absent
- 65a (64) -- delete ANSP 146497
- 92a (91) -- change Redspeckled to “Speckled”
- 94b -- change pores often fused to “pores not often fused”

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